

ON THE TRANSFINITE LENGTH OF THE SEQUENCE OF DIGITS IN THE EXPANSION OF A TRANSCENDENTAL NUMBER AFTER THE DECIMAL POINT

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ABSTRACT. We prove that, if we assume as consistent Cantor's diagonal method, also it is consistent and logically necessary to deduce that among the transcendental numbers there are different transfinite cardinalities in the quantity of the digits that compose them in their expansion after the decimal point. Some transcendentals can be made up of a total of digits \aleph_0 after the decimal point, while another by \aleph_1 or \aleph_2 , or \aleph_α figures.

So, we proceed to mathematically construct such cardinalities. Which in turn forces us to also deduce the existence, within the class \mathbb{R} of the real numbers, of R_α infinite subsets of these numbers with \aleph_α cardinalities different from each other, and we likewise construct them.

We find the logical inadmissibility of identifying, as inadvertently in the current theory, a strictly proper subset R_1 of \mathbb{R} with \mathbb{R} itself. And we obtain for \mathbb{R} a theorem that is comparable to Cantor's Theorem about power sets. Except that this new theorem leads us to resize the currently accepted cardinalities of the power sets P_α . Establishing that none of them reach the number of elements of \mathbb{R} . And for every α the cardinality of each P_α is equal to the cardinality of each R_α , that is, in both cases, to \aleph_α .

Consequently, the real numbers $r \in \mathbb{R}$ have a greater wealth than has so far been conceptualized in Set Theory and Mathematical Analysis. Based on all this, it is also proved that we need to reformulate the Continuum Hypothesis, assuming Cantor's diagonal method is consistent.

Keywords: REAL NUMBERS_TRANSCENDENTAL NUMBERS _INFINITE_MATHEMATICAL ANALYSIS_CONTINUUM HYPOTHESIS_POWER SETS_CARDINALITY_DIAGONAL_CANTOR_IRRATIONALS

INTRODUCTION. RECONSIDERING THE INFINITE RICHNESS OF THE REAL NUMBERS FIELD, RECALIBRATING THE POWER SETS, AND RETHINKING THE CONTINUUM HYPOTHESIS.

From the result of Cantor's diagonal method, about the existence of transfinite quantities, \aleph_α , we inquire: how many decimal figures make up a transcendental number: \aleph_0 or \aleph_1 or \aleph_α or an infinite potential amount?

And one finds that using the strictly logical consequences of such a method, it necessarily follows that among the transcendental numbers there are different transfinite quantities of digits in its construction.

That is, there are transcendental numbers, elements of \mathbb{R} , with an extent of \aleph_0 digits in their development after the decimal point, but there are also transcendentals with a quantity of \aleph_1 or \aleph_2 or \aleph_α figures. Cardinalities in the number of digits of such elements that we proceed to build mathematically.

From this we deduce, extending in a way logically justified the scope of the diagonal procedure, the unexpected conclusion that the \mathbb{R} class of the real numbers is made up of an infinite number of R_α subsets that differ in their cardinalities from each other.

In other words, there are *proper* subsets of \mathbb{R} with \aleph_0 or \aleph_1 amount of elements, but also with \aleph_2 , \aleph_{100} , \aleph_{ω_1} or any \aleph_α quantity of real numbers as members. Cardinalities in the number of elements of such sets that we also construct.

Then, the real numbers have a greater richness than has so far been conceptualized in the Theory of Sets and Mathematical Analysis (and in Measure Theory, Topology, etc.).

So, if we assume as consistent the method of the diagonal of Cantor and the proofs elaborated by the Set Theory regarding the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_i$ (with \mathbb{N} as the set of natural numbers and \mathbb{R}_i the set of real numbers in the interval $[0,1]$), we find the logical inadmissibility of identifying, as is done in the current theory, a strictly proper subset R_1 of \mathbb{R} with \mathbb{R} itself.

Thus, we arrive at a theorem concerning the real numbers, that is analogous to Cantor's Theorem about power sets. Except that this new theorem also conducts us to recalibrate the currently accepted cardinalities of the power sets P_α . Establishing that none of them reach the number of elements of \mathbb{R} . And for all α , $|P_\alpha| = |R_\alpha| = \aleph_\alpha$.

Grounded on these considerations, we also prove that the Continuum Hypothesis, *as currently formulated*, i.e. starting from $2^{\aleph_0} = \mathfrak{c}$, is false (\mathfrak{c} being the cardinality of the continuum). Accordingly, we prove that between \mathbb{N} and the continuum there are infinite R_α sets with different cardinalities \aleph_α and, for all α , $2^{\aleph_\alpha} < \mathfrak{c}$.

Nonetheless, a similar query arises (but that no longer refers to the continuum as a whole), which we call Hypothesis of the Continuity Inside the Continuum. And waits for a solution the question of whether between these R_α (or their P_α equivalents) there exist other intermediate sets with cardinalities other than those \aleph_α obtained by the diagonal process.

To do all that, one starts in section 1 from Cantor's diagonal method, with the well-known Set Theory statement that the set of the real numbers is not denumerable. Also, we set out in part 1.1 some definitions, based on the analysis of the diagonal process, that will assist us in our argumentation.

In point 2, we find that the proof by the Cantor's diagonal has the strict logical limitation of only allowing to conclude that in the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_i$, the constructive diagonal process over \mathbb{R}_i *generates a real r_i number with an \aleph_0 total of figures*. And from that number, you can only produce a co-diagonal divergent number with the same total of \aleph_0 digits. This result is used as a premise to prove that there exists a subset of \mathbb{R}_i whose elements at most consist of an \aleph_0 number of digits (subset that we call $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_0}$ or R_1 . And such that $|R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_0}| = \aleph_1$) (the subscript \aleph_0 indicates the *restriction* about the maximum number of figures; and subscript 1 indicates that it is the first \aleph obtained from the diagonal after \aleph_0 , without presupposing that between \aleph_0 and \aleph_1 an intermediate \aleph may exist or may not exist). And used as a premise to prove that the class $\mathbb{R}_i > |R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_0}| > |\mathbb{N}|$.

Therefore, for \aleph_1 to be equal to the number of elements of \mathbb{R}_i , i.e. to the number of elements of \mathbb{R} , it would be necessary for the maximum number of digits that compose any real number to be \aleph_0 .

To determine whether this is so or not, we start at point 3.1 with the proof that, if we set the function $f: R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_i$, we can apply in \mathbb{R}_i what we designate the *1-extension of Cantor's diagonal*, which proves that there exists another subset of \mathbb{R}_i greater than $|R_1| = \aleph_1$, which we name R_2 . This one, as proved in subsection 3.2, has elements made up at most by \aleph_1 digits, and for this reason, we also call it $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_1}$.

All of this forces us to recalibrate the $P(\mathbb{N})$ power set, in point 3.3, obtaining the results: $|R_1| = |P(\mathbb{N})|$, $|R_1| = 2^{\aleph_0}$, and $|\mathbb{R}_i| > |P(\mathbb{N})|$.

On the other hand, for the number of elements of \mathbb{R}_i is equal to that of R_2 , i.e. \aleph_2 , it would be necessary for the maximum possible sequence of figures of a real number to be \aleph_1 .

More generally: Does \mathbb{R}_i is equal in its number of elements to one $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_\alpha}$, whose elements have at most a total of \aleph_α digits? Don't there be cardinals $|R_\alpha| = \aleph_\alpha$ and $|R_{\alpha+1}| = \aleph_{\alpha+1}$, and therefore, do there not always exist real numbers with more than any given aggregate of \aleph_α figures?

To find out, in part 4 the argument of Cantor's diagonal is generalized, applied on the transfinite subsets of \mathbb{R}_i . Inductively demonstrating the case in which α implies $\alpha+1$.

To this end, we argue (applying the one that we name *δ -extension of Cantor's diagonal*) that if we assume the existence of any set of real numbers R_α ($\equiv R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}$) (a subset of \mathbb{R}_i) whose elements have at most a cardinality of digits restricted to $\aleph_{\alpha-1}$, then there exists, necessarily, a set $R_{\alpha+1}$ successor of R_α whose cardinality is greater than that of R_α . And

the elements of $R_{\alpha+1}$ are each a real number with at most \aleph_α digits in its composition. With this we have mathematically verified and constructed the allowed length of digits in each real number: finite, $\aleph_0, \aleph_1, \dots, \aleph_\alpha$.

Based on all this, one infers that, for all α , R_α is a proper subset of \mathbb{R} and $|\mathbb{R}| > |R_\alpha|$. Namely, there is no last transfinite number $|R| (= \aleph)$, because to every number $|R|$ follows another greater number $|R|$. There is no one last set $R_\alpha = \mathbb{R}$ with an ultimate cardinality.

And any number $r_\alpha \in R_\alpha$ must be a real number. And there are always real numbers with more than any \aleph_α length of digits.

Extending what has already been achieved, one proceeds in section 5 to the consequent recalibration of the classes $R_\alpha, P_\alpha, \mathbb{R}$ and \mathbb{R} . With $P_\alpha \equiv$ the α th power set from \mathbb{N} . And we prove the theorems $|R_\alpha| = |P_\alpha|$ and $|\mathbb{R}| > |P_\alpha|$.

By the mistake of identifying R_1 with \mathbb{R} , or with \mathbb{R} , it is also thought that from \aleph_2 , or any transfinite cardinal that may correspond to the power set $P(P(\mathbb{N})) \equiv P_2$, the \mathbb{R} set of all real numbers is surpassed. When what $|P_2|$ exceeds is to $|R_1|$, but $|P_2|$ it's equal to $|R_2|$. And $|P_\alpha|$ what it exceeds is to $|R_{\alpha-1}|$, and it's equal to $|R_\alpha|$ and less than \mathbb{R} . *One hasn't gone beyond \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{R} .* Any number $r_\alpha \in R_\alpha$ has to be a real number $r_i \in \mathbb{R}$.

In part 6 one makes explicit how it follows from the proved theorems that, assuming that Cantor's diagonal method is consistent, then the Continuum Hypothesis (CH), *as currently conceived*, is false. It's false that if $R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R}$ is a set not enumerable by \mathbb{N} , then there is a bijection $f: R_\alpha \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Namely, it's not true that $(R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R}) \wedge (\aleph_\alpha > \aleph_0) \leftrightarrow \aleph_\alpha = |\mathbb{R}|$. The important thing is that this means that between \mathbb{N} and the continuum $\mathfrak{c} = |\mathbb{R}|$ there exists an infinite number of determined infinite sets, R_α , with different cardinalities from each other. Each of them consists of real numbers. And besides, 2^{\aleph_0} is not the cardinality of the continuum, since $\mathfrak{c} > 2^{\aleph_0}$. Being $2^{\aleph_0} = \aleph_1 = |R_1|$.

This rebuttal of the *existing* Continuum Hypothesis has the advantage of allowing us to rigorously see the scope of the real numbers field. As well as facing mere intuitive conjectures regarding the richness of the continuum itself.

But in item 7 we set out a reformulation, observing two new Hypotheses, which we call *Hypothesis of the Continuity Inside the Continuum (HCIC)*:

1. The *Restricted Hypothesis*: If $R_\beta \subset R_1$ is a set not denumerable by \mathbb{N} , then there is a bijection $f: R_\beta \rightarrow R_1$.

2. The *Generalized Hypothesis*: If $R_\beta \subset R_{\alpha+1}$ is a set not \aleph_α -enumerable by R_α , then there exists a bijection $f: R_\beta \rightarrow R_{\alpha+1}$. And so we have $(R_\beta \subset R_{\alpha+1}) \wedge (|R_\beta| > |R_\alpha|) \leftrightarrow |R_\beta| = |R_{\alpha+1}|$. That is, for any possible mathematical operation, besides being valid for Cantor's Diagonal:

$$\forall \alpha \aleph_{\alpha+1} = 2^{\aleph_\alpha} = 2^{|R_\alpha|} = 2^{|P_\alpha|} = |P_{\alpha+1}| = |R_{\alpha+1}| (\neq |\mathbb{R}|).$$

In this rethink, with both presentations of the HCIC, in no way $\aleph_{\alpha+1}$, or 2^{\aleph_α} , can \aleph_α -enumerate all the reals \mathbb{R} , as both only \aleph_α -enumerate $R_{\alpha+1} \subset \mathbb{R}$. The question remains whether between \aleph_α and 2^{\aleph_α} (both of them within the continuum and lesser in cardinality to it) there is another transfinite cardinal. But it is no longer equivalent to whether between an \aleph_α in the continuum and the continuum \mathfrak{c} there is an intermediate cardinal. Since no 2^{\aleph_α} is the cardinality of the continuum.

Taking everything into account, if we assume that the CH (\neq HCIC) is true, then Cantor's diagonal method is inconsistent. But what affects the CH does not affect the HCIC. Concerning this last or its denial, it is necessary to prove whether it is true or false, or consistent or inconsistent about the diagonal method or to different axioms.

Finally, the important difference with Cantor's Theorem is that the proof presented here is carried out directly generalizing the application of the diagonal method into the \mathbb{R} set of real numbers. But only in this way do we manage to see something that does not allow us to appreciate Cantor's Theorem regarding the power sets: The intricacy of the real numbers and their real scope concerning the transfinite sets.

1. STARTING POINTS

Then, in this paper are taken as the initial basis the premises and method used in Cantor's diagonal process, as admitted by ZFC and similar axiomatics (cf. for example, Jech [13], Fraenkel [8] or Gödel [10]), which lead to the deduction of the existence of different cardinalities between infinite sets. And moving from there we get new theorems about real numbers and the transfinite sets.

So, one starts from the *constructive* and direct proof of the theorem (see Fraenkel [8], pp. 54, 57 and 58; Fraenkel [9], pp. 36 and 37. And Gray [12], p. 823), which states that the set of the real numbers is not denumerable: As one knows, in the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$ (where the $n \in \mathbb{N}$ natural numbers of the domain and the $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ real numbers of the codomain in the interval $[0,1] \in \mathbb{R}$, are placed in correspondence) each digit of every real $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$, in its decimal part, can be depicted as a_{pq} , where p indicates the place in the enumeration of the r_i to which the respective figure belongs; and q the place that occupies the same digit within such a r_i .

From here is derived the fact that we can make an arrangement as in *Table 1*, where p and q correspond respectively to the row and the column in which such a digit is located.

Next, on the \mathbb{R}^i set is operated a diagonal function $f_d = \{(p,q) \in A \times A: p = q\}$ that selects from each r_i a figure such that $p = q$, forming a real diagonal number $0.a_{11} a_{22} a_{33} a_{44} \dots$

Operating with this real, it is generated a new real number $r_a \in [0,1]$, by setting a characteristic function that replaces over the real diagonal number any digit that differs from 1 by 1, and any digit that equals 1 by 2. This is a new real number r_a that diverges from any of the numbers in the range \mathbb{R}^i , that is, it does not belong to this range injected from the domain \mathbb{N} . Proving, with this, that while there is an injection, there is no surjection, and therefore that \mathbb{R}^i is an infinity with cardinality greater than \mathbb{N} .

\mathbb{N}	\mathbb{R}^i
1	0. a₁₁ a ₁₂ a ₁₃ a ₁₄ a ₁₅ ...
2	0.a ₂₁ a₂₂ a ₂₃ a ₂₄ a ₂₅ ...
3	0.a ₃₁ a ₃₂ a₃₃ a ₃₄ a ₃₅ ...
4	0.a ₄₁ a ₄₂ a ₄₃ a₄₄ a ₄₅ ...
...	...

TABLE 1. $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$

1.1. Definitions.

We emphasize that we assume the characteristics and consistency of Cantor's diagonal procedure. Examining this process, it is worth highlighting the difference between what we will call a cognate (akin) diagonal element and a divergent diagonal element.

Definition 1. *Cognate diagonal.* It is the element e_c in a function $f: \text{domain } D \rightarrow \text{codomain } C$, obtained by the Cantor's diagonal process over C , when it is also necessary to conclude that (by definition of the elements of C) $e_c \in C$. So, for example, Cantor's diagonal number r_c on \mathbb{R}^i is a cognate diagonal, since it also occurs, by definition of real number, that $r_c \in \mathbb{R}^i$.

Definition 2. *Cognate co-diagonal.* It is a complement element $\neg e_c$ of the cognate diagonal, obtained from an $f(e_c) = \neg e_c$ function applied to the digits that make up an e_c cognate diagonal element. It is also necessary that, by definition of the elements of C , $\neg e_c \in C$.

Definition 3. *Divergent diagonal.* The non-cognate diagonal element: when e_c not necessarily belongs to C .

Definition 4. *Divergent co-diagonal.* The non-cognate $\neg e_c$ co-diagonal element.

On the other hand, since it is called denumerable any set that has a biunique correspondence with \mathbb{N} , we generalize that definition to refer to the different Cantorian type comparisons between infinite sets of diverse cardinalities that we will make here:

Definition 5. \aleph_α -enumerate ($\forall \alpha$ ordinal number), is to relate the cardinality of an infinite set A with that of another infinite set B , in a function $f: A \rightarrow B$. This determines if there is biunique correspondence between them.

For example, every infinite set maintaining biunique correspondence with \mathbb{N} we will say is \aleph_0 -enumerable by \mathbb{N} ; every infinite set maintaining biunique correspondence with $P(\mathbb{N})$, the set of subsets of \mathbb{N} , is \aleph_1 -enumerable, etc.

When in $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$ Cantor obtains the cognate diagonal element $0.a_{11} a_{22} a_{33} a_{44} \dots$ from the \mathbb{R}^i set of the codomain, and from it generates the real co-diagonal number $r_a \in [0,1]$, he shows that there is no such a thing as an \aleph_0 -enumeration of the reals able to account for all of them in the interval $[0,1]$: $|\mathbb{R}^i|$ (the number of elements of \mathbb{R}^i) $>$ $|\mathbb{N}|$ (the cardinality of \mathbb{N}). And so there exists \aleph_1 and \aleph_0 such that $\aleph_1 > \aleph_0$.

One makes clear: It is denoted \aleph_1 rather than simply \aleph because it is the first cardinal number generated by Cantor's diagonal process from the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$. Without presupposing that from another procedure, or as an axiom, some additional intermediate \aleph 's can or cannot be obtained between \aleph_1 and \aleph_0 , which, if applicable, and with this convention, could be called, for example, $\aleph_{1/2}$ or $\aleph_{0.5}$, or $\aleph_{1/3}$, etc.

In addition, we assume that in Set Theory already has been proven that the number of elements of \mathbb{R}^i is equal to the number of elements of \mathbb{R} . And besides $\aleph_1 = |P(\mathbb{N})| > |\mathbb{N}|$.

2. *WHAT'S NEW:* A LOGICALLY NECESSARY DEDUCTION FROM THE DIAGONAL ARGUMENT, ABOUT THE MAXIMUM TOTAL OF DIGITS POSSIBLE IN EACH REAL NUMBER $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$.

From the assumptions and conclusions of Cantor's diagonal process we want to highlight logically necessary deductions, but not regarded to this day in Set Theory nor in Mathematical Analysis (nor in Topology, etc.).

First, with strict logic, the proof by Cantor's diagonal on the real numbers has the limitation of only allowing to conclude something that seems simple, but has strong consequences, as we'll prove later:

Theorem 1. *In the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$, the diagonal process in $\mathbb{R}^i (= [0,1])$ constructs a transcendental real r_i number consisting of a total of \aleph_0 digits. And from that diagonal number is constructed a transcendental number co-diagonal with the same amount \aleph_0 of digits.*

Proof: In the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$, when injecting the \mathbb{N} domain in \mathbb{R}^i , is on a subset (whether proper or equal) of the codomain \mathbb{R}^i that the diagonal function is applied; and that function constructs a diagonal real number, which is cognate (akin) by being itself a real number.

Such subset in the codomain necessarily contains an \aleph_0 number of elements, since each of them is enumerated by a single natural number, by the starting assumption.

And based on this we get the co-diagonal element that proves that $|\mathbb{R}^i| > |\mathbb{N}|$, when differing, one by one, each a_{rs} digit of the cognate co-diagonal with respect to the corresponding a_{pq} digit of the cognate diagonal, by the function $f(e_c) = \neg e_c$.

Namely, any real number to which represents the cognate diagonal element obtained on \mathbb{R}^i (and therefore any real number corresponding to the cognate co-diagonal from it derived, with a one-to-one change of its figures) can only have in its conformation a total of digits equal to the cardinality of natural numbers (\aleph_0), due to the way it is constructed.

We stress: the diagonal function is operated, as an initial hypothesis, on a range (in the \mathbb{R}^i codomain) to which belongs an aggregate of real numbers equal to the total of natural numbers that \aleph_0 -enumerate such reals one-to-one starting from the \mathbb{N} domain.

The diagonal cannot be worked, in Cantor's proof, on a set of real numbers in a range that exceeds \aleph_0 (the \aleph_0 rows), because in that proof it would be a *petitio principii* to assume that exists, before operating the diagonal, at least a real number $0.a_{n+x} 1 a_{n+x} 2 a_{n+x} 3 a_{n+x} 4 \dots a_{n+x} r_i$ that exceeds the \mathbb{R}^i range in the succession; i.e. to assume that the codomain is greater than the set of images of \mathbb{N} . Which is as much as presupposing that there is no surjection before prove that the surjection does not exist. \square

Then, I return to emphasize that the cognate diagonal element is obtained (due to the starting stipulation) over a range in the codomain \mathbb{R}^i to which belongs an extent of real numbers equal to the total of natural numbers that inject them one-to-one from the other column (the domain \mathbb{N}).

Preparing the Theorem 3's proof, that there exists a set $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ such that $|\mathbb{R}^i| > |R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}| > |\mathbb{N}|$, the following lemmas, theorem, and corollaries are proved.

Lemma 1. Let Cr_i be the number of digits that integrate each real number $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$. There exists a set $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ such that its r_i elements are each a real number formed at most by a total of \aleph_0 figures. And it can be strictly equal to \mathbb{R}^i or a proper subset of it: $\exists R \uparrow_{\aleph_0} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_0\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$.

Proof. From the set that corresponds to the range in \mathbb{R}^i (which we will call \mathbb{R}^i_N) injected by the \mathbb{N} domain, a new subset of \mathbb{R}^i is constructed, which will be named $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$, (which, so far, can be a proper or an equal subset of \mathbb{R}^i ; that is, if the latter case occurs, it would be only a new name of \mathbb{R}^i), with the *restriction* that its $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ elements can only possess up to \aleph_0 digits: $Cr_i \leq \aleph_0$. By the Axiom Schema of Separation.

By the Axiom Schema of Separation, we also form, from \mathbb{R}^i , a subset consisting of any real number entailed by the co-diagonal on \mathbb{R}^i .

In the subset $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$, we join the elements of the \mathbb{R}^i_N set with the elements of the set formed by any real number entailed by the co-diagonal in \mathbb{R}^i (by the Axiom of Union), which also meet (by the Theorem 1) with the stipulated restriction $Cr_i \leq \aleph_0$.

Thus, the new set $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_0\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$ has been constructed. \square

We underline: the *subscript* \aleph_0 is assigned to $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ to indicate the restriction, derived from the diagonal procedure, about the maximum number of digits that can be reached by the real numbers that belong to such a set. And to highlight later their link with the subscripts of the \aleph_α transfinite numbers, I'll also say $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0} \equiv R_I$.

Theorem 2. The cardinality of $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ is greater than \mathbb{N} and less than or equal to \mathbb{R}^i : $|\mathbb{R}^i| \geq |R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}| > |\mathbb{N}|$. Namely, $|\mathbb{R}^i| \geq |R_1| > |R_0|$.

(We will denote by R_0 any subset of \mathbb{R} that has a cardinality equal to \mathbb{N} . It can be a subset of \mathbb{N} , with only elements with finite digits; or not, when the set contains only up to \aleph_0 elements, and each of these possesses finite or infinite figures: $|R_0| = |\mathbb{N}|$).

Proof. The definition of $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ entails that $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ contains as an element the cognate co-diagonal number obtained over the range of the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$ because this co-diagonal element is a real number, that meets, as has been demonstrated in Theorem 1, with the restriction of possessing \aleph_0 digits.

Therefore, $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ has a greater cardinality than \mathbb{N} , by additionally including concerning \mathbb{N} any number entailed by the cognate co-diagonal element, which cannot be \aleph_0 -enumerated by \mathbb{N} :

$$|R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}| > |\mathbb{N}|.$$

And since $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ by definition is a proper or improper subset of \mathbb{R}^i , then $R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}$ can be equal to or less than the universal codomain \mathbb{R}^i :

$$\mathbb{R}^i \geq |R \uparrow_{\aleph_0}| > |\mathbb{N}|. \quad \square$$

I illustrate the argument, trying to make as explicit as possible the new idea set out

here: the path of the diagonal function can only occur, by its very definition, over an \aleph_0

	Column \mathbb{N} $C_{r_i} < \aleph_0$	Column \mathbb{R}^i (With a number of sub-columns r_i without a priori restrictions) $C_{r_i} \geq \aleph_0$	
\aleph_0 rows	1	0.a $_{11}$ a $_{12}$ a $_{13}$ a $_{14}$ a $_{15}$... a $_{1r_i}$	\aleph_0 rows
	2	0.a $_{21}$ a $_{22}$ a $_{23}$ a $_{24}$ a $_{25}$... a $_{2r_i}$	
	3	0.a $_{31}$ a $_{32}$ a $_{33}$ a $_{34}$ a $_{35}$... a $_{3r_i}$	
	4	0.a $_{41}$ a $_{42}$ a $_{43}$ a $_{44}$ a $_{45}$... a $_{4r_i}$	
	
	n	0.a $_{n1}$ a $_{n2}$ a $_{n3}$ a $_{n4}$... a $_{nn}$... a $_{nr_i}$	
	There can no longer be in the domain more $n \in \mathbb{N}$ that enumerates the possible subsequent reals.	... 0.a $_{n+x 1}$ a $_{n+x 2}$ a $_{n+x 3}$... a $_{n+x n+x}$... a $_{n+x r_i}$ 0.a $_{r_i 1}$ a $_{r_i 2}$ a $_{r_i 3}$... a $_{r_i 4}$... a $_{r_i n+x}$... a $_{r_i r_i}$ By the diagonal over \mathbb{R}^i , which only goes all the way to the n -row, there exists more $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ (out of the range, beyond n , but in the codomain).	
With $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$.			

TABLE 2.

extent of numbers $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$; therefore, the resulting diagonal number can only have an \aleph_0 total of figures, since it ends, as can be seen in *Table 2*, in a_{nn} , and not in $a_{n+1 n+1}$, nor in $a_{n+x n+x}$, nor in $a_{r_i r_i}$.

I insist: It is only when mapping the natural numbers $n \in \mathbb{N}$ of the domain (each by definition with a finite amount of digits) on a set of real numbers $R_{i\mathbb{N}} \subseteq R_i$ in the range (with $|R_{i\mathbb{N}}| = \aleph_0$), that one gets the conclusion, with the process of the diagonal, that there is at least some real number, that of the co-diagonal, which cannot be \aleph_0 -enumerated, and therefore that $\exists R_1$ such that $|R_1| > |R_0|$ (because each of the $r_i \in R_i$ has a sequence of digits that can be either finite or infinite, and with $|R_{i\mathbb{N}}| = \aleph_0$ due that the cardinality up to R_i is assumed from the very start as not necessarily greater than the \mathbb{N} cardinality).

Lemma 2. (An obviousness here, but important argumentative precedent for the least obvious reasoning in the theorems proven below, as will be seen). *Any number $r_1 \in R_1$ has to be a real number. We have not gone beyond $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ or $r \in \mathbb{R}$.*

Proof. This happens either because $r_1 \in R_0$, or because necessarily r_1 corresponds to a cognate co-diagonal (definition 2), and not to a divergent co-diagonal (definition 4). The fact that allowed Cantor's conclusion that $|\mathbb{R}^i| > |\mathbb{N}|$. Otherwise, been divergent both, the diagonal and the co-diagonal, by definition, you would get such an x number that it would not be logically guaranteed that $x \in \mathbb{R}^i$, and therefore in his reasoning Cantor would not be proving that x is some real number from which the greatest cardinality of \mathbb{R}^i could be inferred; and therefore, his proof would be wrong. \square

Consequently:

Corollary 1. *The first \aleph attainable with the Cantor diagonal process on \mathbb{R}^i is $|\mathbb{R}^{\aleph_0}| \equiv |R_1| = \aleph_1 \leq |\mathbb{R}^i|$.* \square

We emphasize: we call it $|R_1|$ or \aleph_1 for being the first cardinal number generated by Cantor's diagonal process from the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$. Without presupposing that from another procedure, or as an axiom, an intermediate \aleph may or may not be obtained.

Corollary 2. Thus, so far, for \aleph_1 to be equal to \mathbb{R}^i 's cardinality, i.e. to the cardinality of \mathbb{R} , it would be necessary for the maximum number of digits that constitute any real number to be \aleph_0 :

$$\aleph_1 = |\mathbb{R}^i| \leftrightarrow \forall r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \quad |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_0. \text{ Or, what's the same,}$$

$$\aleph_1 = |\mathbb{R}| \leftrightarrow \forall r \in \mathbb{R} \quad |Cr| \leq \aleph_0. \text{ With } \aleph_1 = |R_1|. \quad \square$$

The question arises: $|\mathbb{R}^i| = |\mathbb{R}^{\aleph_0}|$? Maybe are there no real numbers with more than \aleph_0 digits, when we already know that the quantity $|R_1| = \aleph_1$ exists? To determine this, the following is detailed.

3.1. EXPANDING THE ARGUMENT OF CANTOR'S DIAGONAL ON \mathbb{R}^i

Before arriving at a more general proof, which extends the scope of the diagonal process, we proceed, first, to the demonstration of the next theorem. For the sake of highlighting the arguments as clearly as possible, the proofs that are similar to our previously developed demonstrations have been made explicit.

Theorem 3: *The set \mathbb{R}^i of the real numbers in the interval $[0,1]$, whose r_i elements have any number of figures each in their decimal expansion, without prior restrictions, has a cardinality not equal and strictly greater than the subset R^{\aleph_0} of the real numbers that have such a restriction that their elements r_i are limited to each being made up with between 1 and \aleph_0 number of digits:*

$$|\mathbb{R}^i| > |R^{\aleph_0}| (> |\mathbb{N}|).$$

$$\text{Id est } |\mathbb{R}^i| > |R_1| (> |R_0|).$$

Proof: (With the diagonal procedure). Let's investigate whether $|R^{\aleph_0}| = |\mathbb{R}^i|$. That is if $f: R^{\aleph_0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$ is bijective. We form in the way of Cantor a correspondence, which in this case relates R^{\aleph_0} ($\equiv R_1$) (and no longer just the set \mathbb{N}) in the domain, with \mathbb{R}^i in the codomain.

Let's apply the diagonal in \mathbb{R}^i , which in this case will be designated *the 1-extension of Cantor's diagonal on \mathbb{R}^i* :

In the function $f: R^{\aleph_0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$ every figure in the decimal part of each $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$, is depicted as a_{pq} , where p indicates the place in the enumeration of the r_i to which the respective digit belongs; and q the place that occupies the same digit within such r_i (from here it follows that we can arrange a table as in *Figure 3*, where p and q correspond respectively to the row and the column in which such a digit is located).

Then, on the set \mathbb{R}^i is operated a diagonal function $f_d = \{(p,q) \in A \times A: p = q\}$ that selects from each r_i a digit such that $p = q$, which forms a diagonal real number $0.a_{11} a_{22} a_{33} a_{44} \dots a_{nn} \dots a_{r_i r_i}$.

From that real diagonal number, a real co-diagonal number $r_a \in [0,1]$ is generated (for example, by setting a characteristic function that replaces over the real diagonal number any digit that differs from 1 by 1, and any figure equal to 1 by 2).

Co-diagonal r_a that differs from any of the numbers of the range \mathbb{R}^i , namely, it doesn't belong to this range injected from the domain R^{\aleph_0} of the function f .

Proving with this that while there exists an injection, there is no surjection, and therefore that \mathbb{R}^i is one infinite with cardinality greater than \mathbb{R}^{\aleph_0} .

Demonstrating that in this case the $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ as a set of images of \mathbb{R}^{\aleph_0} in \mathbb{R}^i , are less in cardinality than the $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ as a universal codomain. That the codomain $>$ range (and therefore $r_i > r_0$).

We'll denote R_2 this determined infinite, subset of the codomain \mathbb{R}^i and greater than R_1 . R_2 is either a proper or an equal subset of \mathbb{R}^i , we haven't yet set it. \square

It is therefore inferred:

Corollary 3. $\exists R_2 \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$ such that $|R_2| > |R_1|$. With $|R_2| = \aleph_2$. \square

$|R_2| = \aleph_2$ indicates here the fact that $|R_2|$ is the second \aleph obtained beginning from f :

	$\mathbb{R}^{\aleph_0} \equiv R_1$	\mathbb{R}^i
	$ R_1 = \aleph_1$; with a transfinite maximum limit of \aleph_0 digits in each $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$, that is, $ Cr_i \leq \aleph_0$.	Without assuming a priori a transfinite limit of digits in each $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$, i.e., $ Cr_i \geq \aleph_1$.
	Therefore, column R_1 has at most \aleph_0 sub-columns.	The column \mathbb{R}^i has at least \aleph_1 sub-columns.
	0.a11 a12 a13 a14 ... a1r0	0. a11 a12 a13 a14 ... a1n ... a1r1
	0.a21 a22 a23 a24 ... a2r0	0.a21 a22 a23 a24 ... a2n ... a2r1
\aleph_1 rows	0.a31 a32 a33 a34 ... a3r0	0.a31 a32 a33 a34 ... a3n ... a3r1
	0.a41 a42 a43 a44 ... a4r0	0.a41 a42 a43 a44 ... a4n ... a4r1

	0.an1 an2 an3 an4... anr0	0.an1 an2 an3 an4 ... ann ... anr1

r_1 row	0.ar11 ar12 ar13 ar14 ... ar1r0	0.ar11 ar12 ar13 ar14 ... arr1 ... ar1r1
	There can no longer be more $r_i \in R_1$ in the domain able to \aleph_α -enumerate additional subsequent possible reals in R_1 0.ar11 ar12 ar13 ar14 ... arr1 By the diagonal, which only reaches, by hypothesis, until the r_1 row, there exist more $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ such that $r_i \notin R_1$.
Where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $r_0 \in R_0$, $r_1 \in R_1$, $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$, and $ Cr_i \geq Cr_1 $.		
Each r_0 in the second position represents the increasing number of columns up to \aleph_0 (the maximum possible proved number of digits of those real numbers, so far, from Cantor's diagonal).		
Also, each r_1 in the first position represents the increasing number of lines up to \aleph_1 corresponding to R_1 . And r_i represents the possible growing number of sub-columns corresponding to \mathbb{R}^i .		
Then, in column R_1 of the domain, the largest number of digits that a real number can reach corresponds to $a_{r_1 r_0}$. While in the \mathbb{R}^i column of the set of images the respective quantity of figures ($a_{r_1 r_i}$) is open to being equal to or greater than the corresponding to $a_{r_1 r_0}$.		

TABLE 3. $f: \mathbb{R}^{\aleph_0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$.

$\mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$ through the recursive application of the diagonal method, without presupposing that from another procedure a different intermediate \aleph can or cannot be obtained.

3.2. CONSTRUCTING THE EXTENSION OF DIGITS IN THE $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ REAL NUMBERS

The proof with the 1-extension of Cantor's diagonal has the limitation of only allowing to conclude that the existence and construction of real numbers are logically justified only up to \aleph_1 digits. They are the real numbers that form the R_2 set.

There may be a larger amount of digits in a real number, but their existence is not yet mathematically or logically verified. Which we'll do later.

Theorem 4. *In addition to being greater than R_1 , the R_2 set obtained by the process 1-extension of Cantor's diagonal is integrated in such a way that its r_i elements are each a real number, consisting at most of a quantity \aleph_1 of digits. And R_2 has cardinality less than or equal to the cardinality of \mathbb{R}^i :*

$$R_2 \equiv R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_1} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_1\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i; \text{ and}$$

$$|\mathbb{R}^i| \geq |R_2|$$

Proof: In the function $f: R_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$ the cognate diagonal in \mathbb{R}^i can only have a total of digits equal to that of $|R_1|$ because, by hypothesis, it is operated on a total of real numbers in the codomain \mathbb{R}^i equal to the entire of reals from the R_1 domain column (that \aleph_1 -enumerate those codomain numbers). Since, by its construction, the diagonal over the set of images of R_1 in \mathbb{R}^i , which we'll call $\mathbb{R}^i_{R_1}$, selects a digit of each real number that is an element of this set. Namely, the diagonal procedure can only occur over an \aleph_1 number of digits.

It cannot be operated on a set with more real numbers than \aleph_1 , because that would be a petitio principii. And it is because it is not a situation of begging the question, that the previous results are valid and important (including Cantor's original deduction of $|\mathbb{R}^i| > |\mathbb{N}|$; and also that there is at least one real number, corresponding to the co-diagonal, which cannot be \aleph_1 -enumerated, and therefore that $\exists R_2 > R_1 > \mathbb{N}$).

From the set formed by the range $\mathbb{R}^i_{R_1}$, corresponding to the domain R_1 , a subset $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_1} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$ is constructed (which can be equal or proper), with the restriction that its elements can only possess between one and \aleph_1 digits (by the Axiom Schema of Separation).

The set $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_1}$ not only contains the elements of the $\mathbb{R}^i_{R_1}$ set. We can add (with the Axiom of Union) the elements of the R_a set formed (applying the Axiom Schema of Separation) by any real number involved by the co-diagonal on \mathbb{R}^i . Which also comply, as we have just proved, with the stipulated restriction $|Cr_i| \leq \aleph_1$.

In this way, it is determined how the new set $R_2 = \mathbb{R}^i_{R_1} \cup R_a$ is structured. R_2 is also denoted $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_1} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_1\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$.

And since R_2 by definition is a subset, proper or equal, of \mathbb{R}^i , then \mathbb{R}^i cannot be less than R_2 and consequently, besides being R_2 greater than R_1 , not necessarily $R_2 = \mathbb{R}^i$, since the option of R_2 being less than the universal codomain \mathbb{R}^i is still alive:

$$|\mathbb{R}^i| \geq |R_2| > |R_1|. \quad \square$$

It can be seen, then, that Cantor and the set theorists after him, made the inaccuracy of identifying what we have called R_1 , the only set logically justified by the diagonal process in Cantor's original reasoning, with \mathbb{R}^i and with \mathbb{R} . *Even with R_2 one hasn't gone beyond \mathbb{R}^i or \mathbb{R} :*

Theorem 5: *Any number $r_2 \in R_2$ has to be a real number $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$:*

$$r_2 \in R_2 \rightarrow r_2 \in \mathbb{R}^i.$$

Proof: That fact happens:

1) Or because r_2 is a $r_i \in R_1$,

2) Or because r_2 is obtained necessarily as a cognate co-diagonal (definition 2), and not as a divergent co-diagonal (definition 4). Where a digit $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ is taken - for example, from 0 to 9 in the decimal system - from each real number in the range (by definition of the diagonal procedure); the diagonal number obtained is, therefore, a real number. It generates a cognate co-diagonal number, which by definition consists only of digits, e.g., of the figures 1 and 2, which structures it as another real number.

That is to say, r_2 is a real number because it is not obtained as a divergent co-diagonal; this is a fact logically equivalent to the one that previously allowed Cantor's conclusion that $|\mathbb{R}^i| > |\mathbb{N}|$. Otherwise, with a divergent co-diagonal, by definition, you would get such a number x that you would not be logically guaranteed that $x \in \mathbb{R}^i$ and therefore would not be shown that x is some real number that contributes to increasing \mathbb{R}^i 's cardinality. \square

3.3. THE RECALIBRATION OF THE POWER SET $P(\mathbb{N})$

From the discovery of the difference in cardinality between R_1 and $\mathbb{R}^i \geq R_2$, I will proceed to recalibrate the scope of different infinite sets, such as R_1 , $P(\mathbb{N})$, and \mathbb{R}^i . This is facilitated by correcting and adapting for R_1 a proof already existing in Set Theory for \mathbb{R}^i , but that confuses R_1 with \mathbb{R}^i .

Lemma 3. *Let C_{N_s} be the total of elements (natural numbers) that belongs to each set $N_s \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. Then $|C_{N_s}| \leq \aleph_0$.*

Proof. \mathbb{N} has at most \aleph_0 elements, by definition of the cardinality of \mathbb{N} . Therefore, each subset N_s of \mathbb{N} has at most \aleph_0 elements: $|C_{N_s}| \leq \aleph_0$. By the Axiom Schema of Separation. \square

We will use the Schroeder-Bernstein Theorem to prove, with the following equality, that the cardinality of $P(\mathbb{N})$ is equivalent to that of R_1 , and not to that of \mathbb{R}^i .

Theorem 6. $|R_1| = |P(\mathbb{N})|$.

Proof.

1. Let's first prove $|R_1| \leq |P(\mathbb{N})|$.

A function $f: R_1 \rightarrow P(\mathbb{N})$ is established, where each $r_1 \in R_1 \subset (0,1)$ is injected towards each $N_s \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, with $N_s \in P(\mathbb{N})$.

The decimal part of each $r_1 \in R_1$ is written in binary form as a sequence of digits 0 and 1 which, by Lemma 1, can only have a cardinality of digits less than or equal to \aleph_0 :

$$|C_{r_i}| \leq \aleph_0.$$

We stipulate such correspondence that the n th digit 1 within each real r_i indicates that the natural number n does belong to N_s , while the n th digit 0 indicates that $n \notin N_s$.

Previously it is already known that to avoid repetitions, in case of generating the same binary number more than once, we take only that decimal form that does not end only in zeros; and that, even if $(0,1)$ does not include 0, which corresponds to the empty set, $|(0,1)| = |[0,1)|$.

Therefore, every $r_1 \in R_1$ corresponds to a different subset N_s of \mathbb{N} , as it occurs that $|C_{N_s}| \leq \aleph_0$ (by the Lemma 3) and $|C_{r_i}| \leq \aleph_0$, which implies that any $|C_{N_s}|$ can be matched by any $|C_{r_i}|$:

$$\forall N_s \exists r_i \text{ such that } |C_{N_s}| = |C_{r_i}|.$$

And therefore, there is no N_s that cannot be covered in its number of elements by an r_1 with a similar number of digits. So $|R_1| \leq |P(\mathbb{N})|$.

2. It is proved $|P(\mathbb{N})| \leq |R_1|$.

Each subset of \mathbb{N} corresponds, as established in part 1 of this proof, to an infinite binary chain of digits 0 and 1, so that such a string can be injected towards the corresponding decimal number r_1 . In this way, each subset $N_s \in P(\mathbb{N})$ corresponds to a different decimal $r_1 \in R_1$ made up exclusively of the 0 and 1 digits, with $|Cr_1| \leq \aleph_0$. Hence, we have $|P(\mathbb{N})| \leq |R_1|$.

Consequently, by 1 and 2 in this proof and the Schroeder-Bernstein Theorem, $|P(\mathbb{N})| = |R_1|$; i.e., *there are exactly as many real numbers in R_1 as there are subsets of the naturals in $P(\mathbb{N})$* . \square

Theorem 7. $|R_1| = 2^{\aleph_0}$

Proof.

$$|R_1| = |P(\mathbb{N})| \text{ (by Theorem 6).}$$

$$|P(\mathbb{N})| = 2^{\aleph_0} \text{ (by a corollary from the Cantor's Theorem).}$$

$$|R_1| = 2^{\aleph_0} \text{ (by transitivity).} \quad \square$$

Theorem 8. $|R_{\dot{i}}| > |P(\mathbb{N})|$.

Proof.

$$|R_{\dot{i}}| > |R_1| \text{ (by theorem 3).}$$

$$|R_1| = |P(\mathbb{N})| \text{ (by theorem 6).}$$

$$|R_{\dot{i}}| > |P(\mathbb{N})| \text{ (by transitivity).}$$

Put another way: The quantity of elements $N_s \in P(\mathbb{N})$ is limited by cardinality \aleph_0 (by Lemma 3), while $R_{\dot{i}}$ contains, in addition to the reals r_i that form a set with cardinality R_1 by Lemma 1 (which correspond bijectively to these elements N_s by the theorem 6), to those other numbers r_i that have more than \aleph_0 figures (by the theorem 4) and that, therefore, form at least one set with greater cardinality. \square

Corollary 4. For $|R_{\dot{i}}| = |R_2| = \aleph_2$ to occur, the maximum possible quantity of digits in a real number would need to be \aleph_1 :

$$|R_{\dot{i}}| = |R_2| \leftrightarrow |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_1. \text{ With } |R_2| = \aleph_2. \quad \square$$

The question arises: $R_{\dot{i}} = R_{\aleph_1}$? Maybe do not exist the cardinals $|R_\alpha| = \aleph_\alpha$ and $|R_{\alpha+1}| = \aleph_{\alpha+1}$? And therefore, do not there always exist real numbers with more than \aleph_α digits?

Or, more generally: $R_{\dot{i}} = R_{\aleph_\alpha}$? Do not exist the cardinals $|R_\alpha| = \aleph_\alpha$ y $|R_{\alpha+1}| = \aleph_{\alpha+1}$? And therefore, perhaps there are not always real numbers with more than whichever \aleph_α quantity of digits?

4. GENERALIZATION OF THE ARGUMENT OF CANTOR'S DIAGONAL ON THE R_α TRANSFINITE SUBSETS OF $R_{\dot{i}}$.

Next, we will prove inductively the more general case, in which α entails $\alpha+1$. To do this, we argue that, if we assume the existence of a set $R_\alpha \equiv R_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}} = \{r_i \in R_{\dot{i}} \mid |Cr_i| \leq$

$\aleph_{\alpha-1}$ }, then necessarily, by the diagonal procedure, it follows that there exist a set $R_{\alpha+1} \equiv R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha}} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_{\alpha}\}$ such that $R_{\alpha} \subset R_{\alpha+1} \wedge |R_{\alpha}| \not\approx |R_{\alpha+1}| < |\mathbb{R}^i|$.

Viz., given a set $R_{\alpha} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$ with \aleph_{α} quantity of real numbers as elements, their Cantorian arrangement as a domain, for example in a column, can only reach the number \aleph_{α} of occurrences or rows.

If a function $f: R_{\alpha} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$ is established and a diagonal is operated that selects a digit, and only one, of each row of the set of r_i images in \mathbb{R}^i , that diagonal can therefore only have, based on the starting assumption, a total of digits equal to \aleph_{α} .

But being the case of a cognate diagonal number, this will imply, applying the algorithm of Cantorian type, necessarily the formation of a cognate co-diagonal number with equal extent \aleph_{α} of digits.

This proves that there is at least one co-diagonal real number r_a such that $r_a \notin R_{\alpha}$. This makes it possible to deduce the existence of a set $R_{\alpha+1} \subset \mathbb{R}^i$ as a codomain greater than the set of the range corresponding to R_{α} in \mathbb{R}^i , and with $|\mathbb{R}^i| > |R_{\alpha+1}| > |R_{\alpha}|$.

In-depth, the proofs with Cantor's Diagonal, and with their extensions argued in this paper, have the logical limitation of only allowing to conclude that:

Theorem 9. *If we assume the existence of any set of real numbers*

$R_{\alpha} \equiv R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}\}$, *as a subset of \mathbb{R}^i , then there is necessarily a successor $R_{\alpha+1}$ set whose cardinality is greater than that of R_{α} ; and the elements of $R_{\alpha+1}$ are each a real number with no more than \aleph_{α} figures in their composition:*

$$\forall \alpha \exists R_{\alpha} \equiv R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}\} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$$

$$\rightarrow \forall \alpha \exists R_{\alpha+1} \equiv R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha}} \text{ such that } |R_{\alpha+1}| (= \aleph_{\alpha+1}) > |R_{\alpha}| (= \aleph_{\alpha})$$

$$\wedge R_{\alpha+1} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_{\alpha}\}.$$

Proof: (With the diagonal procedure). Let $f: R_{\alpha} (= R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$. Mapping each element of R_{α} over \mathbb{R}^i generates a set of images in \mathbb{R}^i .

Each figure in the decimal part of each $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ is represented as a_{pq} , where p indicates the place in the \aleph_{α} -enumeration of the r_i to which the respective digit belongs; and q the place that occupies the same figure within such r_i (so we can form the *Table 4*, where p and q correspond, respectively, to the row and the column in which such a digit is located).

Let's apply Cantor's diagonal function $f_d = \{(p,q) \in A \times A: p = q\}$ over this range in \mathbb{R}^i (the δ -extension of Cantor's diagonal on \mathbb{R}^i), which selects from each r_i a digit such that $p = q$, thus forming a real diagonal number $0.a_{11} a_{22} a_{33} a_{44} \dots a_{r_{\alpha} r_{\alpha}}$ (being $a_{r_{\alpha} r_{\alpha}}$ the digit corresponding to the row r_{α} , and the sub-column $r_i \geq r_{\alpha-1}$).

From that real diagonal number, a real co-diagonal $r_a \in (0,1)$ number is generated (for example, by setting a characteristic function that replaces on the diagonal any digit that differs from 1 by 1 and any digit equal to 1 by 2).

Co-diagonal r_a differing from any of the numbers in the \mathbb{R}^i range, that is, it does not belong to this range injected from the R_{α} domain of function f . This proves that while there is an injection, there is no surjection and therefore \mathbb{R}^i is an infinity greater than R_{α} . Proving so there exists a $R_{\alpha+1}$ set such that $|R_{\alpha+1}| > |R_{\alpha}|$.

The cognate diagonal on the image set of R_{α} in the \mathbb{R}^i codomain (a range which we denote $\mathbb{R}^i_{R_{\alpha}}$), can only have an entire of digits equal to that of $|R_{\alpha}|$. Then: universe codomain $\mathbb{R}^i > \text{range } \mathbb{R}^i_{R_{\alpha}}$ (and therefore $r_i > r_{\alpha-1}$). Since any element yielded by the cognate diagonal number can only have in its composition an extent of digits equal to the cardinality of \aleph_{α} ; and as a result, the same occurs to any element corresponding to the cognate co-diagonal number derived from it, with a one-to-one mapping of its figures, because for its construction by the diagonal, a digit of each real number belonging to that set of images in \mathbb{R}^i is selected.

And that cognate diagonal number is obtained, by the starting hypothesis, on a range $\mathbb{R}^i_{R_{\alpha}}$, in such a \mathbb{R}^i column, to which belongs a total of real numbers equal to the total of real numbers that \aleph_{α} -enumerate them one-to-one from the other column (the domain R_{α}).

Applying the Axiom Schema of Separation and the Axiom Union, the range R_{α} forms hence, with any r_i number involved by the cognate diagonal, a new set, which will be

denoted $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_\alpha} (\equiv R_{\alpha+1})$, which has the *restriction* that its elements can only reach a maximum total \aleph_α of figures:

$$R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_\alpha} \equiv R_{\alpha+1} = \{r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i \mid |Cr_i| \leq \aleph_\alpha\}.$$

It is clear that such definition includes any r_i number involved by the cognate co-diagonal, as this is an element that fulfills, as has just been proved, the restriction in the total of digits that determines the $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha+1}}$ set. That being why, we emphasize, this $R_{\alpha+1}$ has a higher cardinality than R_α .

And $R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha+1}}$, with its restriction, is a subset (proper or equal) of the \mathbb{R}^i codomain. Codomain that has no restrictions on the number of digits of its elements. And it may have a cardinality equal to or less than such \mathbb{R}^i .

Obviously, as we have already proved the existence of R_1 , with $\alpha = 1$, and its cardinality equal to \aleph_1 , from the diagonal process, then it is inferred by the preceding paragraphs that $\exists R_{\alpha+1} = R_{1+1} = R_2$ such that $\aleph_2 = |R_2| > |R_1| = \aleph_1$. And as we now get $\alpha = 2$, the existence of $|R_3| > |R_2|$ immediately follows, and so on. \square

Theorem 10. *The \mathbb{R}^i class of the real numbers in the interval $[0,1]$, whose r_i elements have any number of figures each, without prior restrictions, has as its proper subset to any R_α :*

$$\forall \alpha R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R}^i$$

Proof: Let $R_{\alpha+1} \supseteq R_\alpha$ be. By definition it includes all the elements of the previous R_α ; but also includes the cognate co-diagonal element on R_α , which does not belong to R_α , and therefore $R_\alpha \subset R_{\alpha+1}$.

On the other hand, $R_{\alpha+1} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$, because it comes from R_α and its cognate co-diagonal. Consequently, $R_\alpha \subset R_{\alpha+1} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$.

Therefore, by transitivity, $R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R}^i$. \square

Theorem 11. *\mathbb{R}^i has a strictly greater cardinality than any proper subset R_α of the real numbers that comply with such restriction that its elements are limited to being constituted, each, by between one and $\aleph_{\alpha-1}$ digits:*

$$\forall \alpha |\mathbb{R}^i| > |R_\alpha| (\equiv |R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}|).$$

Proof: In the function $R_\alpha \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$, R_α always yields, with its injection, a range $\mathbb{R}^i_{R_\alpha}$ whose cardinality is less than the cardinality of the \mathbb{R}^i codomain of which it is a subset since it is always less than its successor set $R_{\alpha+1} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^i$, by Theorem 9.

That is, the diagonal process can never be operated over the entire universe of the class \mathbb{R}^i in the codomain of all real numbers in the interval $[0,1]$, as this would be a *petitio principii* since the proof always starts with the premise that each element of R_α injects to one element of \mathbb{R}^i . In other words, there is no logical justification for presupposing that $|R_\alpha| \neq |\mathbb{R}^i|$.

And such circular reasoning would consist in assuming that it exists, before applying the diagonal function and its co-diagonal, at least a real number $0.a_{r1} a_{r2} a_{r3} a_{r4} \dots a_{rri}$ that exceeds to the set of images of R_α in \mathbb{R}^i , i.e. the assumption that the codomain is greater than the range. Which is as much as presupposing that there is no surjection before proving that the surjection does not exist.

Only without the existence of that universal path of the diagonal function over the entire \mathbb{R}^i class, it is possible to obtain the previous results (including the original of Cantor with $\alpha = 0$) that there is at least one real number, that of the co-diagonal, which cannot be \aleph_α -enumerated.

Then $\forall R_\alpha \exists R_{\alpha+1}$ such that $|\mathbb{R}^i| > |R_{\alpha+1}| > |R_\alpha|$. With $|R_\alpha| = \aleph_\alpha$ and $|R_{\alpha+1}| = \aleph_{\alpha+1}$.

Namely, there are no last subset R_α with cardinality equal to \mathbb{R}^i . To paraphrase Euclid [7], when referring to prime numbers: There is no last transfinite number $|R| (= \aleph)$,

because each number $|R|$ is followed by another greater number $|R|$. There is no one last set $R_\alpha = \mathbb{R}^i$ with an ultimate cardinality:

$$\forall \alpha \neg \exists |R_\alpha| \geq \mathbb{R}^i. \quad \square$$

\mathbb{R}^i is an infinite codomain whose universe is greater than any subset of it with R_α -range, and consequently (see *Table 4*), $\forall r_\alpha, r_i, r_{\alpha-1} < r_i$.

	$R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}} \equiv R_\alpha$	\mathbb{R}^i
	With a maximum C_{r_i} of $\aleph_{\alpha-1}$: $ C_{r_i} \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}$. (And $ R_\alpha = \aleph_\alpha$)	Without supposing a priori a limit of digits in each $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$: $ C_{r_i} \geq \aleph_{\alpha-1}$. And $r_i \geq r_{\alpha-1}$.
	0.a ₁₁ a ₁₂ a ₁₃ a ₁₄ ... a _{1$r_{\alpha-1}$}	0. a ₁₁ a ₁₂ a ₁₃ a ₁₄ ... a _{1r_i}
	0.a ₂₁ a ₂₂ a ₂₃ a ₂₄ ... a _{2$r_{\alpha-1}$}	0.a ₂₁ a ₂₂ a ₂₃ a ₂₄ ... a _{2r_i}
\aleph_α rows	0.a ₃₁ a ₃₂ a ₃₃ a ₃₄ ... a _{3$r_{\alpha-1}$}	0.a ₃₁ a ₃₂ a ₃₃ a ₃₄ ... a _{3r_i}
	0.a ₄₁ a ₄₂ a ₄₃ a ₄₄ ... a _{4$r_{\alpha-1}$}	0.a ₄₁ a ₄₂ a ₄₃ a ₄₄ ... a _{4r_i}

r_α row	0.a _{r_α1} a _{r_α2} a _{r_α3} a _{r_α4} ... a _{$r_\alpha r_{\alpha-1}$}	0.a _{r_α1} a _{r_α2} a _{r_α3} ... a _{$r_\alpha r_\alpha$} ... a _{$r_\alpha r_i$}
	There can no longer be in the domain more $r_i \in R_\alpha$ such that they \aleph_α -enumerate subsequent possible reals in the universal codomain \mathbb{R}^i 0.a _{r_i1} a _{r_i2} a _{r_i3} ... a _{$r_i r_{\alpha+x}$} ... a _{$r_i r_i$} By the diagonal, which only goes all the way to the r_α row, there are more $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$. So: Range in $\mathbb{R}^i \subset$ Universal codomain \mathbb{R}^i . Likewise, $ $ Range in $\mathbb{R}^i < $ Universal Codomain $\mathbb{R}^i $.
	With $r_{\alpha-1} \in R_{\alpha-1}$, $r_\alpha \in R_\alpha$, $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$.	And $r_i \geq r_\alpha > r_{\alpha-1}$.

TABLE 4. $R_\alpha \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$.

We haven't gone beyond \mathbb{R}^i or \mathbb{R} . Any number corresponding to the diagonal on a R_α set, or its co-diagonal, it's a *real* number $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ or $r \in \mathbb{R}$:

Theorem 12. Any number $r_\alpha \in R_\alpha$ is, and must be, a real number:

$$\forall \alpha r_\alpha \in R_\alpha \rightarrow r_\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^i.$$

Proof: This occurs:

- 1) Or because the $r_1 \in R_1 \subset R_\alpha$ are real numbers (by Lemma 2), obtained from the first cognate diagonal;
- 2) Or because, $\forall \alpha$, the numbers $r_i \in R_\alpha$ are obtained necessarily from an δ -extension of Cantor's diagonal, cognate, starting with the diagonal over R_1 . In each of which δ -diagonals, a digit $r_i \in \mathbb{R}^i$ is taken from each real number in the range - for example, from 0 to 9 in the decimal system - (by definition of the diagonal procedure). The number obtained is thus only constituted of real digits. Therefore, that diagonal number is a real number that generates in each stage a cognate co-diagonal, which by definition consists only of the digits 1 and 2.

r_i is a real number for not being obtained from a divergent diagonal element. The fact is logically equivalent to the one that allowed Cantor the inference that $|\mathbb{R}^i| > |\mathbb{N}|$. Otherwise, with a divergent co-diagonal, by definition, you would get such a number x

that you would not logically guarantee that $x \in \mathbb{R}^i$ and therefore it would not be shown that x is some real number that could contribute to increasing the total of numbers of \mathbb{R}^i .
□

The need to obtain cognate diagonals underlies the possibility of proving that transfinite numbers exist. This leads to the logical necessity for the non-existence of a last $R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R}$ and therefore the non-existence of one last $r \in \mathbb{R}$.

The answer to the question: $\mathbb{R}^i = \mathbb{R} \upharpoonright_{\aleph_\alpha}$? it's just: $\forall \alpha \mathbb{R}^i \neq \mathbb{R} \upharpoonright_{\aleph_\alpha}$. And there are cardinals $|R_\alpha| = \aleph_\alpha$ and $|R_{\alpha+1}| = \aleph_{\alpha+1}$. And there exists always *real numbers* with more than any total \aleph_α of digits. And so, we have verified and *constructed*, as we announced at the beginning of paragraph 3.2, *their existence mathematically*.

Corollary 5. In the collection of subsets of the class \mathbb{R}^i a property analogous to the Archimedean order in natural numbers is fulfilled: *Let $|R_\alpha|$ be any transfinite cardinal number \aleph_α . Then always there exists one $|R_{\alpha+1}| = \aleph_{\alpha+1}$ greater than $|R_\alpha|$.* □

Below (*Figure 1*) there is a diagram that graphically shows the meaning of our argument, by demarcating the part unsuitable from the beginning in Cantor's reckoning.

Cantor's diagonal primal process actually traces a Diagonal D_0 on a set of real numbers R_0 , with cardinality equal to \aleph_0 . But this has been confused with the trace and operation of a $D_{\mathbb{R}^i}$ diagonal along the \mathbb{R}^i axis. Believing that it has encompassed the entire \mathbb{R}^i class in one fell swoop. When the most that can be done with logical foundation is to build step by step the subsets R_α of \mathbb{R}^i , also using the diagonals $D_1, D_2, \dots, D_{\aleph_\alpha}$, in such a way that D_{\aleph_α} tends to increasingly match the \mathbb{R}^i axis, $D_{\aleph_\alpha \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i}$, but never reaches it. You cannot trace the $D_{\mathbb{R}^i}$ diagonal mathematically. And, as you can see to the right of the graph, the quantity of real numbers on which a diagonal can be operated is increasingly expanded in cardinality.

FIGURE 1.

5. GENERALIZED RECALIBRATION

Based on what we have already said, we will immediately proceed to recalibrate, to re-measure, R_α , P_α , and \mathbb{R}_α . With $P_\alpha \equiv \alpha$ th power set from \mathbb{N} .

First, let's prove that $|P_\alpha| = |R_\alpha|$.

Lemma 4. *Let P_α be any set in the succession of power sets from \mathbb{N} . And let C_{P_s} be the number of elements that belong to each set $P_s \subseteq P_\alpha$. Then $|C_{P_s}| \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}$.*

Proof. P_α has at most $\aleph_{\alpha-1}$ elements, by definition of the cardinality of P_α . Therefore, each P_s subset of P_α has at most (by the Axiom Schema of Separation) $\aleph_{\alpha-1}$ elements:
 $|C_{P_s}| \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}$. □

Theorem 13. $\forall \alpha \quad |R_\alpha| = |P_\alpha|$. *Viz.*, $|P \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}| = |R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}|$.

Proof. We will use Schroeder-Bernstein's Theorem to prove equality:

1. We prove first $\forall \alpha \quad |R_\alpha| \leq |P_\alpha|$. That is, $\forall \alpha \quad |R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}| \leq |P \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}|$.

We set a function $f: R_\alpha \rightarrow P_\alpha$, where each $r_\alpha \in R_\alpha (\equiv R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}})$ is injected into each $P_s \in P_\alpha$, with $P_s \subseteq P_{\alpha-1}$.

The decimal part of each $r_\alpha \in R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}$ is written in binary form, as an alternation of the digits 0 and 1. Decimal that, by definition in the theorem 9, can only have a cardinality of digits less than or equal to $\aleph_{\alpha-1}$: $|C_{r_\alpha}| \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}$.

We set the α th number 1 of the alternation indicating that the real number $r_\alpha \in P_s$, whereas the α th number 0 indicates that $r_\alpha \notin P_s$.

Previously, in the Theory of Sets we know that to avoid repetitions, in case of generating the same binary number in more than one mode, we take only that decimal form that does not end only in zeros. And that, even if $(0,1)$ does not include 0, which corresponds to the empty set, $|(0,1)| = |[0,1)|$.

Hence, every $r_\alpha \in R_\alpha$ corresponds to a different subset P_s of P_α , as it happens that $|C_{P_s}| \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}$ (by Lemma 4) and $|C_{r_\alpha}| \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}$ (by the definition in theorem 9), which means that $\forall P_s \exists r_\alpha$ such that $|C_{P_s}| = |C_{r_\alpha}|$. And therefore, any P_s can be matched in its number of elements by a r_α with a similar number of figures. Thus, we establish the injection of R_α in P_α . So, $|R_\alpha| \leq |P_\alpha|$.

2. We prove that $\forall \alpha \quad |P_\alpha| \leq |R_\alpha|$. *Id est*, $\forall \alpha \quad |P \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}| \leq |R \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}|$.

Each subset of P_α corresponds, as proved above, to an infinite binary alternation of numbers 0 and 1; consequently, such alternation can be injected towards the respective decimal number r_α .

In this way, each subset $P_s \in P_\alpha$ corresponds to a different decimal $r_\alpha \in R_\alpha$ composed only by the digits 0 and 1, with $|C_{r_\alpha}| \leq \aleph_{\alpha-1}$. As a result, we have $|P_\alpha| \leq |R_\alpha|$.

Then, by 1 and 2 in this proof and the Theorem of Schroeder-Bernstein, $\forall \alpha \quad |P_\alpha| = |R_\alpha|$, i.e., there are exactly as many real numbers in each R_α as there are subsets of the reals in each P_α . □

Theorem 14. $|P_2| > |R_1|$.

Proof.

$|P_2| > |P_1|$ (by Cantor's Theorem).

$|P_1| = |R_1|$ (by substitution in Theorem 13).

$|P_2| > |R_1|$ (by transitivity). □

Theorem 15. $|R_2| > |P_1|$.

Proof.

$|R_2| > |R_1|$ (by Corollary 4).

$|R_1| = |P_1|$ (by Theorem 6).

$|R_2| > |P_1|$ (by transitivity). □

Theorem 16. $\forall \alpha \ |R_\alpha| > |P_{\alpha-1}|$.

Proof.

$|R_\alpha| > |R_{\alpha-1}|$ (by Theorem 9).

$|R_{\alpha-1}| = |P_{\alpha-1}|$ (by substitution in Theorem 13).

$|R_\alpha| > |P_{\alpha-1}|$ (by transitivity). □

It can be seen, then, that Cantor and the set theorists after him, made the unjustified step of identifying what we have called R_1 , the only set logically warranted by the diagonal process in the Cantor's original reasoning, with \mathbb{R}^i and \mathbb{R} . And so, they also believed that starting with \aleph_2 (or any transfinite cardinal that \aleph_α -enumerate the power set $P(P(\mathbb{N})) \equiv P_2$) the \mathbb{R} class of all the real numbers is surpassed. When, as I've proved, it's not. To what P_2 exceeds, when you exceed $P(\mathbb{N}) \equiv P_1$, is to R_1 . But P_2 is equal to R_2 and less than \mathbb{R}^i . And P_α to what it exceeds is to $R_{\alpha-1}$, and it's equal to R_α . *We haven't gone beyond \mathbb{R}^i or \mathbb{R} .*

Before these proves, it was no longer obvious here, what was evident in Lemma 2, because it's contrary to the current belief in the mathematics that \aleph_2 , as the cardinality of the power set $P(P(\mathbb{N}))$ (or any other transfinite cardinal that could \aleph_α -enumerate it), surpasses the cardinality of the class \mathbb{R} of all real numbers, and that the members of $P(P(\mathbb{N}))$ are more than the $r \in \mathbb{R}$.

Theorem 17. $\forall \alpha \ |\mathbb{R}^i| > |P_\alpha|$.

Proof. As $|P_\alpha| \equiv |P \upharpoonright_{\aleph_{\alpha-1}}|$, the number of elements in each $P_s \in P_\alpha$ is limited by the cardinality $\aleph_{\alpha-1}$ (by Lemma 4), while \mathbb{R}^i contains, in addition to the r_i that correspond to these elements (reaching the digits of these r_i a cardinality $|R_{\alpha-1}|$ by the Theorem 16), those others that have more than $\aleph_{\alpha-1}$ figures (by the theorem 11), and therefore form sets with higher cardinalities. □

6. THE CONTINUUM HYPOTHESIS

Cantor, and with him, the posterior mathematicians, not realizing the mathematical and logical details that have been highlighted here, have confused $R_1 \subset \mathbb{R}^i$ with \mathbb{R}^i itself. And so, they've also confused $|R_1|$ ($< |\mathbb{R}^i|$) with $|\mathbb{R}^i|$.

As I have proved, to be logically consistent with the premises and arguments of Cantor's diagonal process, it would be a mistake to think that beginning with R_1 each diagonal results in a new transfinite quantity that cannot be \aleph_α -enumerated with the real numbers (thus forming a totality of additional elements, such as sets of sets, which would no longer be \aleph_α -enumerated by the \mathbb{R}^i set). And that's how we would have $|\mathbb{R}^i| = |\mathbb{R}| = |P(\mathbb{N})|$, and $|P(P(\mathbb{N}))| > |\mathbb{R}|$.

When in fact $|P_1| = |R_1|$, $|P_2| = |R_2|$, and $|P(P(\mathbb{N}))| < |\mathbb{R}|$.

We want to accentuate and make it clear that here we call $|R_1|$ and therefore \aleph_1 , i.e. $|P(\mathbb{N})|$, to the first \aleph that can be obtained from Cantor's diagonal operation in the function $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^i$. Thus, with this criterion, if the existence of an \aleph between \aleph_0 and \aleph_1 were proved, such \aleph could be assigned, for example, a fractional or decimal subscript ($\aleph_{1/2}$ or $\aleph_{0.1}$, etc.).

The cardinality of \mathbb{R} is called the continuum \mathfrak{c} , which relates real numbers (the arithmetic continuum) with the points on a line (the linear continuum). Speaking with strict logic, the following theorem is inferred from the theorems 3, 11, and 17 (thus being consistent with the results found so far from the mathematical statements assumed in Cantor's diagonal process, from which our extensions also come):

Theorem 18: *Assume that Cantor's diagonal method is consistent. Then*

THE CONTINUUM HYPOTHESIS (CH) IS FALSE.

That is, in the context of the mathematical and logical premises and arguments distinctive of the diagonal process, it's false that if $R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R}$ is a set not enumerable by \mathbb{N} , then there is a bijection $f: R_\alpha \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Namely, it is false that

$$\forall \alpha R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R} \wedge |R_\alpha| > |\mathbb{N}| \leftrightarrow |R_\alpha| = |\mathbb{R}^i|.$$

Meaning, it's not true that

$$\forall \alpha R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \aleph_\alpha > \aleph_0 \leftrightarrow \aleph_\alpha = |\mathbb{R}^i|.$$

Proof. If we assume that Cantor's procedure of the diagonal is correct, then, by theorems 3, 11, and 17, derived from accepting such a validity (from which its extensions come in this paper), there can't exist any bijection $f: R_\alpha \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$.

Consequently, any R_α is a subset of \mathbb{R} and with a cardinality not equal to it:

$$\forall \alpha R_\alpha \subset \mathbb{R} \wedge |R_\alpha| < |\mathbb{R}|.$$

And as a result, no $\aleph_\alpha > \aleph_0$ is equal to $|\mathbb{R}^i|$:

$$\forall \alpha \neg \exists \aleph_\alpha \geq |\mathbb{R}^i|.$$

So, we have that

$$|\mathbb{N}| = |R_0| < |R_1| < |R_2| < |R_3| < \dots |R_\alpha| \dots < |\mathbb{R}|.$$

Therefore, between \mathbb{N} and the continuum $\mathfrak{c} = |\mathbb{R}|$ there is an infinite number of determined infinite sets, R_α , with different cardinalities from each other. Each of them is made of real numbers.

On the other hand, any infinite determined set P_α , or its equivalent in cardinality, can be \aleph_α -enumerated, measured, by a subset R_α of \mathbb{R} , by the Theorem 17.

Also, there is no transfinite number \aleph_α greater than the cardinality of \mathbb{R} (by theorems 11 and 13). Consequently, there is no issue of whether there exists an intermediate \aleph_α between \mathbb{R} cardinality and a greater \aleph_α cardinality. Or if between sets \aleph_α with (impossible) cardinality greater than \mathbb{R} there may be an \aleph_α in-between. \square

The Continuum Hypothesis, *as it is formulated today*, is erroneous not only because the rigorous deduction denies that

"All infinite point-sets P have either the power of the first number class (I) or the power of the second number-class (II)" (viz. that of natural numbers or that of the continuum) (Cantor [2], p. 905).

But also because by the theorems 3, 11, and 17, between the two infinite linear varieties are not one, but infinite varieties \aleph_α . The continuum, the field of the real numbers, or any interval thereof, such as $(0,1)$, is infinitely far away from \aleph_1 or any \aleph_α in terms of cardinality.

Corollary 6. *As you can see (assuming the diagonal operation) $\mathfrak{c} \neq \aleph_1$, because $\mathfrak{c} = |\mathbb{R}| > \aleph_1$.* \square

And, besides:

Theorem 19. *Assume that Cantor's diagonal method is consistent. Then 2^{\aleph_0} is not the cardinality of the continuum:*

$$\mathfrak{c} \neq 2^{\aleph_0}.$$

$$\mathfrak{c} > 2^{\aleph_0}.$$

Proof. 2^{\aleph_0} is a determined infinity, as established from Cantor's Theorem about power sets. And it is, therefore, a cardinal \aleph_α , at least the \aleph_1 . But as has already been demonstrated here with theorems 11 and 17, any \aleph_α is less than $|\mathbb{R}|$.

Then 2^{\aleph_0} is less than $|\mathbb{R}|$:

$$2^{\aleph_0} \neq |\mathbb{R}|; |\mathbb{R}| > 2^{\aleph_0}.$$

And as $|\mathbb{R}| = \mathfrak{c}$, then 2^{\aleph_0} is less than \mathfrak{c} . \square

Theorem 20. *As the first application of the diagonal method, in $f: \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_i$, 2^{\aleph_0} is the cardinality of R_1 , which is equal to \aleph_1 (i.e. the transfinite number that follows \aleph_0 when the diagonal process is applied):*

$$2^{\aleph_0} = |R_1|.$$

Proof.

By Cantor's Theorem derivation in Set Theory, $2^{\aleph_0} = |P_1| = \aleph_1$.

By Theorem 13, $|P_1| = |R_1| = \aleph_1$.

Replacing $|P_1|$ by $|R_1|$: $2^{\aleph_0} = |R_1| = \aleph_1$. \square

I stress, from the premises of the Cantor's diagonal process the continuum is neither, and cannot be, equal to \aleph_2 , nor \aleph_3 , nor \aleph_{26} , nor \aleph_ω , or any other \aleph_α . And in no way can 2^{\aleph_0} be greater than all other $|\mathbb{R}_\alpha| > |\mathbb{R}_1|$.

Precisely, the rebuttal of the Continuum Hypothesis has the advantage of allowing us to see rigorously the scope of the field of the real numbers, in the face of mere intuitive conjectures such as those of Baire, Gödel, or Cohen (cf. Dauben [6], p. 269) regarding the wealth of the continuum itself.

With the Cantorian method of the diagonal consequently applied, there is no way to arrive with the \aleph_α 's cardinality above the \mathbb{R} 's cardinality, given the characteristics of the cognate co-diagonal number necessary for its argumentation, which always turns out to be a real number.

7. A NEW HYPOTHESIS: THE CONTINUITY INSIDE THE CONTINUUM

But two hypotheses arise, similar to some extent, but actually very different, concerning the CH (hypotheses which by their characteristics we will call the *Hypotheses of the Continuity Inside the Continuum*, or *HCIC*).

1. The most limited: between $|\mathbb{N}|$ ($= |\mathbb{R}_0|$) and $|\mathbb{R}_1|$ (obtained by the operation of the diagonal, and both less than $|\mathbb{R}|$), there is no intermediate cardinality (for example that of $|\mathbb{R}_{0.5}|$). Or what is the same, between \aleph_0 and \aleph_1 there is no intermediate \aleph . That is:

RESTRICTED HYPOTHESIS OF THE CONTINUITY INSIDE THE CONTINUUM (OR: RESTRICTED HYPOTHESIS OF THE CONTINUITY BETWEEN \aleph_0 AND 2^{\aleph_0}):

If $R_\beta \subset R_1$ is a set not enumerable by \mathbb{N} , then there is a bijection $f: R_\beta \rightarrow R_1$. That is, $|\mathbb{R}_\beta| > |\mathbb{N}| \leftrightarrow |\mathbb{R}_\beta| = |\mathbb{R}_1|$.

So, for any possible mathematical operation, besides being valid for Cantor's diagonal operation, $\aleph_1 = 2^{\aleph_0} = |\mathbb{R}_1| = |\mathbb{P}_1|$ ($\neq |\mathbb{R}|$).

In this rethink in no way can \aleph_1 , nor 2^{\aleph_0} , \aleph_α -enumerate all reals in \mathbb{R} . Both \aleph_α -enumerate only to R_1 . The question remains whether there is another cardinal between \aleph_0 and 2^{\aleph_0} , but it is no longer equivalent to whether between \aleph_0 and the continuum \mathfrak{c} there is an intermediate cardinal.

2. The most general Hypothesis: between each $|\mathbb{R}_\alpha|$ and $|\mathbb{R}_{\alpha+1}|$ there is no intermediate cardinality. Or what is the same, between each \aleph_α and $\aleph_{\alpha+1}$ there is no intermediate \aleph . That means:

GENERALIZED HYPOTHESIS OF THE CONTINUITY INSIDE THE CONTINUUM (OR: GENERALIZED HYPOTHESIS OF THE CONTINUITY BETWEEN \aleph_α AND 2^{\aleph_α}):

If $R_\beta \subset R_{\alpha+1}$ is a set that is not \aleph_α -enumerable by R_α , then there is a bijection $f: R_\beta \rightarrow R_{\alpha+1}$. *Viz.*, $|\mathbb{R}_\beta| > |\mathbb{R}_\alpha| \leftrightarrow |\mathbb{R}_\beta| = |\mathbb{R}_{\alpha+1}|$.

So, we would have, for any possible mathematical operation, besides being valid for Cantor's diagonal operation:

$$\forall \alpha \ \aleph_{\alpha+1} = 2^{\aleph_\alpha} = 2^{|\mathbb{R}_\alpha|} = 2^{|\mathbb{P}_\alpha|} = |\mathbb{P}_{\alpha+1}| = |\mathbb{R}_{\alpha+1}| \ (\neq |\mathbb{R}|).$$

By no means can $\aleph_{\alpha+1}$, or 2^{\aleph_α} , \aleph_α -enumerate all reals in \mathbb{R} ; as both only \aleph_α -enumerate $R_{\alpha+1}$. The question remains whether between \aleph_α and 2^{\aleph_α} (both in the interior of the continuum and less in cardinality that it), there is another cardinal.

But it is no longer equivalent to whether, amid an \aleph_α inside the continuum and the continuum \mathfrak{c} , there is an intermediate cardinal number. Or if between any \aleph_α equal, or greater and external, to the continuum (an \aleph_α we now know is nonexistent if the Cantor's diagonal method is consistent) and another $\aleph_{\alpha+1}$ (also external and greater than the continuum; and in the same way nonexistent) there is an intermediate cardinal. Since 2^{\aleph_α} is not the cardinality of the continuum.

Now then, in any one of these hypotheses, the continuum does not intervene as the entire set of points on a numerical line, since, as proved in this paper, no subset R_α of points is the continuum \mathfrak{c} , nor \mathbb{R}_i nor \mathbb{R} , but a transfinite proper subset of them, with smaller size.

So, we proved that within the continuum, between \mathbb{N} and the continuum, there exist infinite R_α -sets, both numerical and points, with different cardinalities \aleph_α . And waits for an answer, the question of whether between these sets R_α (or their equivalents \mathbb{P}_α) there are in turn other intermediate sets with cardinalities other than such \aleph_α 's.

Theorem 21. *Assume the Continuum Hypothesis CH (\neq HCIC) is true, then Cantor's diagonal method would be inconsistent.*

Proof. By Modus Tollens applied to Theorem 18. □

But what affects the CH does not affect the HCIC. About the HCIC (or the \neg HCIC) it is necessary to prove yet if it is true or false, or consistent or inconsistent concerning the

diagonal method or to different axioms. Thus, when Cantor, and his successors, don't consider the strictly logical consequences of his argument, based on the role played by the number of digits of each cognate diagonal, which I proved in this paper, they have conceived the Continuum Hypothesis erroneously in some way.

In that direction, Gödel stated:

(1)

"Continuum problem is simply the question: How many points are there on a straight line in Euclidean space."

(2)

"In other terms: How many different sets of integers do there exist?" (Gödel [11] p. 176).

But for what has already been said, it is wrong to put it this way, different respect to How many different sets R_α of *real numbers* does there exist?

Actually, (2) is different from (1), and is not (1) said in other terms. The sets of integers are exhausted with R_1 ; they are followed in cardinality by the sets of real numbers $r_2 \in R_2$; then the sets of real numbers $r_3 \in R_3$, and so on. With $R_1 \subset R_2$, $R_2 \subset R_3$, etc. There are infinite subsets R_α of reals (of transcendentals) and points in the straight line (and in their respective α -ary relationships, in the plane, or α dimensions), each with different power \aleph_α .

2^{\aleph_0} is located in the aleph-hierarchy, as derived from the application of the diagonal, on its second step, $|R_1|$. And it can't be at anything bigger. While the continuum, the class of points on a straight line in Euclidean space, is much wealthier in elements.

Furthermore, Cohen contended that

A point of view which the author feels may eventually come to be accepted is that CH is obviously false. The main reason one accepts the Axiom of Infinity is probably that we feel it absurd to think that the process of adding only one set at a time can exhaust the entire universe. Similarly with the higher axioms of infinity. Now \aleph_1 is the set of countable ordinals and this is merely a special and the simplest way of generating a higher cardinal. The set C [the continuum; for Cohen equal to a P_α and a 2^{\aleph_α} . Author's Note] is, in contrast, generated by a totally new and more powerful principle, namely the Power Set Axiom. It is unreasonable to expect that any description of a larger cardinal which attempts to build up that cardinal from ideas deriving from the Replacement Axiom can ever reach C . Thus C is greater than \aleph_n , \aleph_ω , \aleph_α where $\alpha = \aleph_\omega$ etc. This point of view regards C as an incredibly rich set given to us by one bold new axiom, which can never be approached by any piecemeal process of construction. (Cohen [5], p.151).

But the continuum, as we have already seen, cannot be generated by the Power Set Axiom, as it is an unattainable limit for the diagonal process, i.e., for the operation 2^{\aleph_α} . The continuum is not represented by 2^{\aleph_0} or by \aleph_2 , \aleph_{15} , ..., \aleph_α , as Cohen could also hypothesize. 2^{\aleph_0} is the cardinality of R_1 . The continuum is something incredibly richer, much more succulent, infinitely more succulent, than $|R_1|$, i.e. than $|P_1|$, \aleph_1 , or 2^{\aleph_0} . Or than any $|R_\alpha|$, i.e., any $|P_\alpha|$, \aleph_α or 2^{\aleph_α} .

The essential point is that no 2^{\aleph_α} equals c . The Continuum Hypothesis referring to c has been shown to be false. While the hypothesis referring to the non-continuum 2^{\aleph_α} continues in suspense. And it's the HCIC.

In conclusion and in a precise sense, Gödel and Cohen are inexact about the continuum. But it must be clear that with this rebuttal and subsequent modification of the Continuum Hypothesis, the mistake does not occur in the formal development of their proofs of independence.

The phases of the reasoning of Gödel and Cohen remain to have logical force, but they must be corrected (as we have already corrected another proof of Set Theory in theorems 6 and 13) since CH is disabled; and be used to decide the truth or falsehood, or the independence, of the new Hypothesis of the Continuity Inside the Continuum (absence of

intermediate cardinalities among the \aleph_α subsets of the continuum). Considering the consistency of its affirmation (or its denial \neg HCIC) concerning systems such as ZFC or related (and no longer use those arguments on the subject of the HC or \neg HC dilemma, now resolved).

That is, the proofs of axiomatic independence are valid as long as they can correct and avoid the basic error of confusing \aleph_α or \aleph with R_1 or with any R_α . And consequently, as long as they generate the respective explicit or implicit substitutions of R_1 or R_α instead of \aleph or \aleph_α in their arguments, models, and methods, such as the inner-model or the forcing. And with the correspondence of \aleph_1 only with R_1 or P_1 , and with their respective ordinal numbers. And each \aleph_α only with its pertinent R_α or P_α .

But with Gödel and Cohen's proofs properly rectified, it can be proven that both HCIC and \neg HCIC are consistent with ZFC or related systems, with the diagonal procedure and, therefore, with the construction of transfinite numbers. All of which we want to detail in a later paper.

On the other hand, Theorem 9 is a proof logically similar to that of Cantor's Theorem, about the existence of an infinite succession of power sets from the respective diagonals. Except that's how we get: $|P(\mathbb{N})| \neq |\aleph_\alpha|$, while $|P(\mathbb{N})| = |R_1|$; and for all power sets P_α , $|P_\alpha| = |R_\alpha|$. And $\aleph \sim \mathbb{P}$ (the class of all real numbers is equivalent to the class of all power sets). About the latter, we will abound in a next paper, and besides, we will also deal, v.gr., the transfinite ordinals.

The important difference is that the proofs presented here are performed directly with diagonals on subsets of the real numbers. But only in this way have we managed to observe something that does not allow us to appreciate Cantor's Theorem, regarding the power and real numbers sets: its real calibration, its right measure. And, for Mathematical Analysis, we can see the complexity and scope of the real numbers concerning the transfinite sets.

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